

ENVIRONMENTAL DISASTERS AND PUBLIC SERVICE: THE STATE RESPONSE AND MARKET ACTIVISM

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Abstract: *While the natural phenomenon or sudden disasters decimate the population on the planet, it is of utmost importance to draw appropriate response to the vagaries of the nature. Though the frequencies of such disasters are not certain, the approach towards protecting the lives and property of the mankind may be pervasive in case of lack of a proper response. While continuous efforts are made by the State in helping the needy at the time of crisis, sometimes the unusual functions of the state indicates it's flaws by enlarging its scope and reach in dealing with disaster management. An attempt has been made here to understand the fundamental role of the State and market in managing disasters starting from resilience to mitigation. This paper also argues that the State directly or indirectly provides a conducive atmosphere for market to function and to become socially responsive and accountable during disasters. Finally this paper throws some light on the approach of the state towards maximum intervention and minimum service which provides ample opportunity to market to establish complex and complicated set of institutional arrangements during disasters.*

Key words: Response, Disaster Management, Governance, Activism, Public Service

Introduction

Not only the literature on Ancient India had many references but the history of human civilization indicates a struggle towards escaping from the hazardous disasters of various forms and the havoc caused by those calamitous episodes. At the time of crisis while the role of the state is regarded as primary in order to establish the state's legitimacy, on the other hand in mitigating the worst effects of natural disasters, competitive politics and politics of patronage have occupied the centre stage. A State possesses a definite and different set of institutionalized channels where the State apparatus and the public/stakeholders interact in a constructive manner on policy making and implementation. The State, it seems like, is in the process of continually interaction and negotiation for social and economic development. (Cypher and Dietz, 1997). As Mark Bevir pointed out that State may be considered as an institution at necessity. But since the days of economic reform, the State faces new and complex demands which can be only met with competitive and entrepreneurial institutions; not by the State with limited resources (Bevir, 2007). A distinction may be noticed here between the scope of the State, availability of resources and capacity of a State. In case of State failure, when the market extends the services and remedies the States' flaws by enlarging its scope and reach, the market occupies the public ground and treated as market at possibility. It is to understand that the unremarkable and unusual functions of the State are what make markets possible. But it is not to be ignored that the State directly or indirectly provides a conducive atmosphere for market to function and to become socially responsive and accountable.

Disaster Management and State Intervention

Starting from the Aristotle's concept that 'State is an indispensable necessity to man as a social being' to Weberian concept of State that 'agency within the society that has the monopoly of legitimate constraint', the State has adopted significant and different roles at times. Can we say that the State falls further behind the curve of modern rationalized processes or some

fundamental reengineering to significantly improve the quality of the services during the time of disasters is the need of the hour? From disaster recovery efforts to redistribution of resources, sometimes the failure of the state compels the market to play significant role in reducing the looming and immediate threats to life and property of individuals during disasters. It is indeed significant that a pro-active stance to reduce the toll of disasters in India also requires a more comprehensive approach which facilitates pre-disaster risk reduction as well as post-disaster recovery. At times of major crisis, the state is viewed as most powerful and visible organization in protection of life and property of the citizens during pre-disaster and deployment of resources for post-disaster relief, reconstruction and recovery. In recent years a paradigm shift has been observed in the role of the state from a reactive post-disaster relief centric to a proactive disaster preparedness and strengthened response capacity. Good governance and responsive administration are outcomes of an effective interface with the citizens/communities at risk from the devastating and hazardous impact of disasters. But it is to note here that irrespective of the changes and improvement in managing the disasters by the state, an attitude of business as usual sometimes hinder the process of managing disasters mostly in case of restoration of disrupted services and protection of life and property of disaster affected communities. Once the role of the state comes prominent and to the forefront, the other measures which are taken by the individuals or other stakeholders/actors voluntarily in managing the effects of the disaster go disregarded.

At the same time also the state provides ample opportunities to other players like political parties and leaders ample opportunities to gain political mileage in order to let people seek political favours to get rehabilitation benefits or restoration reliefs. In this context it is to understand that managing the disaster by the state has provided an unsolicited platform to gain political mileage or to seek political patronage. This kind of political intervention causes diverted attention not only from the core issue i.e. relief from the disasters and disaster management but from various private initiatives taken by market or charity etc. (Mitra, 2000). The upsurge of neo-liberalism during the last two decades or so has fundamentally changed the terms of debate on the role of the State (Chang, 1994a). The State at present is not assumed as an impartial, omnipotent social guardian and is now analysed either as a predator or as a vehicle for politically powerful groups to advance their sectional interests. No other motives than maximization of material self-interests are accorded to any agent even in the public domains of life, denouncing the role of politics as a legitimate way to correct the market outcomes as per the collective will (Burlamaqui, Castro and Chang, 2000:3-4).

Decoding Market Activism

As Jayal argues in a third world context, the idea of governance as a more or less technical facilitator of development, delinked from conceptions of democracy and welfare, is a highly impoverished notion. The western recognition that the simple equation between governance and democracy, and of both these with economic prosperity, is belied in the experience of many countries of the third world, has led to the application of a different set of standards for the latter, whereby democracy and development are seen as possibly incompatible, and democracy is sought to be substituted by governance. This notion of governance partakes of some of the elements of classical liberal-democracy, incorporated into a minimalist institutional design (Jayal, 2007). In this perspective, then, development is not open to political contestation. Both development and democracy are implicitly defined in ways that ensure conformity with an essentially western ethos in the third world context viewing governance as a technical facilitator of development and delinking it from democracy and welfare, emerge as a highly impoverished notion. The experience has showed us that there is no inevitable relationship between democracy and development. Some of the undemocratic states are developmentally ineffective; on the other the equal undemocratic states are highly effective in bringing economic and social

development. The idea that the better quality of governance would promote development is not seen in the countries like India. The literature as well as the historical trends in India raises a doubt on the efficiency of the market or private players in managing the disasters. While economic development is regarded as an important factor in mitigating the disaster, sometimes it is also argued that facilitating markets in managing many spheres of activity helps in improving economic performance. While sometimes the role of state in managing the disaster becomes marginal due to a number of factors like lack of communication, limited resources etc. the role of market plays a pivotal role in collection of resources, reaching out to the needy and proper and timely delivery of information and services with the help of advanced technology etc.

Many aspects of governance have very critical importance in particular if the notion of freedom will be taken into considerations. In economic terms, freedom can be seen as an opportunity set and development can be seen as the removal of various types of non-freedoms. As Amartya Sen argues as essential as such an intrinsic value as freedom is, its instrumental value also matters because of the effectiveness of freedoms of particular kind to promote freedoms of other kinds (Sen, 1999). This approach is consistent with the transition from a dialogue based on ideology to the dialogue based on ideals that has transpired in the global development community over the last few decades. During disasters, from mobilizing a good number of resources to effective communication and information to the affected citizens, the role of market sometimes becomes undoubtedly prominent. Because, the market sometimes ensures the follow up actions in strengthening preparedness, prevention, mitigation, emergency response etc. in a more effective way. In order to eradicate the systemic inefficiencies, the market plays significant role in addressing the critical gaps in the effective management of disasters in India.

Critical Assessment and the Way Ahead

As per the definition and meaning of Good Governance, an efficient public service, a reliable judiciary and a responsive administration are some of the primary attributes. In the present context, the key question for the State is which role it should adopt and also in which context. Under certain circumstances, the State needs to take a leadership role. In other situations the customers do not trust the government and State where the State does not has required competence. With an increase in the number of natural disasters over the past years, the traditional perception of the idea of calamity relief has been converted into disaster prevention and mitigation of the impact of natural disasters. The extent to which a population is affected by disaster also takes into consideration of the prevailing social and economic conditions and its consequential effect on human activities in both pre and post-disaster periods. A solution to the state's unplanned inadequate development activity and the market activism in managing the disasters needs to be planned or executed. It is to note that with the passage of time, the resources, effort and expertise needed in disaster management already exist with the state and its apparatus. Mostly streamlining of the integration of various approaches, existing institutional arrangements and deployment of well-equipped/skilled personnel as an initial response to disaster makes the disaster management more effective and professional. Delineating responsibilities and powers of each entity whether state or market and clear distribution help in managing a disaster. The process of development must take the aspect of disaster reduction and mitigation within its ambit or else with the state's unusual response and market activism, the development ceases to be sustainable and the disaster eventually causes more hardship and loss to the civilization.

Conclusions

In this article it was discussed that the hazardous disasters have various. During the calamities a state possesses a definite and different set of institutionalized channels where the State

apparatus and the public/stakeholders interact in a constructive manner on policy making and implementation. The role of state in managing the disaster becomes marginal due to a number of factors like lack of communication, limited resources etc. The role of market plays a pivotal role in collection of resources, reaching out to the needy and timely delivery of information and services with the help of advanced technology etc. Mostly streamlining of the integration of various approaches, existing institutional arrangements and deployment of well-equipped/skilled personnel as an initial response to disaster makes the disaster management more effective and professional. Delineating responsibilities and powers of each entity whether state or market and clear distribution help in managing a disaster. The process of development must take the aspect of disaster reduction and mitigation within its ambit or else with the state's unusual response and market activism, the development ceases to be sustainable and the disaster eventually causes more hardship and loss to the civilization.

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